

A Unified Variational Integral-Reduction Framework for Planar Elastica under Magnetic and Gravitational Loading

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Abstract

We present a variational framework for analyzing planar elastic rods subjected to distributed magnetic and gravitational loads, systematically reducing nested integrals in the energy functional to single-integral expressions. By exploiting Fubini's theorem and introducing cumulative field functions, the approach simplifies the derivation of the governing equations while clearly separating contributions from bending, magnetic torques, and gravity. Inspired by studies on three-dimensional hard-magnetic rods [5], the proposed framework not only enhances the clarity of energy-functional analysis but also provides a concise and systematic mathematical formulation for the theoretical study of planar rods under combined magnetic and gravitational effects.

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1. Introduction

Elastica is a fundamental model in mechanics for describing slender rods or beams, where the geometry is determined by the tangent angle or curvature distribution, and the mechanical behavior is typically characterized by bending energy and applied loads [1]. The classical catenary was solved by Joachim Jungius (published posthumously in 1669) [2]. It asks for the

curve of a chain that is fixed at two points under its own weight in a gravitational field. This later yielded classical Euler elastica theory, which provides a systematic framework for studying deformations of rods in both plane and space. Since James Bernoulli's first precise formulation of the treaty of elastica in 1692 [3], Bernoulli's [8] and Euler's use of variational methods [6] [7], various scientists have evolved a rigid framework to treat loads on elastica. A great overview about the historical evolution is given by Raph Levien [4]. The celebrated book "A Treatise on the Mathematical Theory of Elastica" gives an overall summary of the entire field [9]. Wang commented on the treaty of heavy elastica in 1986 [10] and showed its application to various examples like hanging columns or cantilevers.

In many practical situations, rods are subject to distributed potential energies along their length—such as gravity, magnetic torques, or other body forces—leading to bending or complex planar deformations. Therefore the coupling between internal degrees of freedom (which is given e.g. via magnetic forces) and material strains to open up new avenues for structural instabilities has been receiving much recent attention in the mechanics and advanced functional material communities [11] [12]. While in modern application the treatise of magnetic forces is sufficient and well understood [13][14], since gravitational loads are negligible [5], we offer a more general framework that on the one hand encompasses the magnetic loads but on the other hand also includes gravity from classic heavy elastica.

2. Rewriting Nested Load Integrals via Fubini's Theorem

We consider an inextensible planar rod parametrized by the arc-length $s \in [0, L]$. Many distributed loadings—such as magnetic body torques or gravity-induced forces—give rise to energy contributions that naturally involve nested integrals of the general form

$$I \int_0^L \int_0^{s_1} g_1(s_1)g_2(s_2)ds_2ds_1 = \int_0^L \int_{s_2}^L g_1(s_1)g_2(s_2)ds_1ds_2 \quad (1)$$

where g_1 and g_2 are continuous functions determined by the rod geometry and the applied fields.

The essential idea is to treat the nested integral (1) as a structural object rather than focusing on elementary manipulation steps. This is Fubini's theorem. The integration domain

$$\{0 \leq s_2 \leq s_1 \leq L\} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$$

Figure 1: Schematic of the rod geometry and loading. Black arrows indicate the direction of the gravitational field; the applied magnetic field is uniform and oriented perpendicular to the plane of the figure, pointing out of the page. Boundary conditions are shown in the figure, with one end of the rod fixed and the remainder free to deform.

is triangular, which naturally allows the introduction of a *cumulative field function*

$$G(s_2) := \int_{s_2}^L g_1(\xi) d\xi, \quad (2)$$

and leads to a compact, single-integral representation

$$I = \int_0^L G(s_2) g_2(s_2) ds_2 = \int_0^L G(s) g_2(s) ds. \quad (3)$$

This formulation isolates the structural coupling encoded by the nested integral and provides a systematic framework to simplify energy functionals for planar rods subject to distributed loads. The same viewpoint extends naturally to multi-layer nested integrals. For instance, an n -fold nested integral of the form

$$\int_0^L g_1(s_1) \int_0^{s_1} g_2(s_2) \cdots \int_0^{s_{n-1}} g_n(s_n) ds_n \cdots ds_2 ds_1 \quad (4)$$

can be recursively reduced by defining a hierarchy of cumulative field functions $G_k(s)$, yielding a compact or single-integral expression. In this work, we focus on the two-layer case $n = 2$, while noting that the framework applies

Figure 2: Triangular integration domain in the (s_1, s_2) plane

Figure 3: Geometric interpretation of the cumulative field function $G(s)$

verbatim to higher-order nested integrals encountered in rod mechanics and related variational problems.

In this work, all functions considered are assumed to be continuous, differentiable, and Lebesgue integrable on the finite domain $[0, L]$, ensuring the validity of the integral manipulations and application of Fubini's theorem.

3. Application to Hard Magnetic Rods under Planar Deformations

We now apply the mathematical framework to analyze the planar deformation of hard magnetic rods under external magnetic fields. Thereby, we follow the work of [5]. Consider an inextensible rod of length L with circular cross-section of radius R , uniformly magnetized along its centerline with residual flux density B^r . \mathbf{F} describes the deformation gradient. The total energy functional combines elastic bending and magnetic contributions:

$$E_{\text{total}} = \int_0^L \frac{EI}{2} (\theta')^2 ds - \frac{A}{\mu_0} \int_0^L (\mathbf{F}\mathbf{B}^r) \cdot \mathbf{B}^a ds, \quad (5)$$

where $A = \pi R^2$ is the cross-sectional area. Assuming the magnetic moment aligns with the tangent direction $\mathbf{t}(s) = (\cos \theta(s), \sin \theta(s))$ and the rod is inextensible, the magnetic energy simplifies to:

$$E_{\text{mag}} = -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \left[B_x^a(s) \cos \theta(s) + B_y^a(s) \sin \theta(s) \right] ds. \quad (6)$$

To handle the nested integrals arising from the variation, we use the integral representations of the trigonometric functions. Specifically, the tangent angle $\theta(s)$ can be expressed as:

$$\theta(s) = \theta(0) + \int_0^s \theta'(\tau) d\tau, \quad (7)$$

which allows us to expand $\sin \theta(s)$ and $\cos \theta(s)$ as:

$$\sin \theta(s) = \sin \theta(0) + \int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \cos \theta(\tau) d\tau, \quad \cos \theta(s) = \cos \theta(0) - \int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \sin \theta(\tau) d\tau. \quad (8)$$

Substituting $\sin \theta(s)$ and $\cos \theta(s)$ into Eq. (6), we use Fubini's theorem to rewrite the nested integrals as integrals over τ .

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{mag}} &= -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \left[B_x^a(s) \left(\cos \theta(0) - \int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \sin \theta(\tau) d\tau \right) + B_y^a(s) \left(\sin \theta(0) + \int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \cos \theta(\tau) d\tau \right) \right] ds \\ &= -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \left[-B_x^a(s) \left(\int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \sin \theta(\tau) d\tau \right) + B_y^a(s) \left(\int_0^s \theta'(\tau) \cos \theta(\tau) d\tau \right) \right] ds + C_1 \\ &= -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \theta'(\tau) \left[-\sin \theta(\tau) \left(\int_\tau^L B_x^a(s) ds \right) + \cos \theta(\tau) \left(\int_\tau^L B_y^a(s) ds \right) \right] d\tau + C_1. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

We define cumulative field functions:

$$K_x^a(\tau) = \int_\tau^L B_x^a(s) ds, \quad K_y^a(\tau) = \int_\tau^L B_y^a(s) ds. \quad (10)$$

After simplification, the magnetic energy reduces to a single integral:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{mag}} &= -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \theta'(\tau) \left[-\sin \theta(\tau) K_x^a(\tau) + \cos \theta(\tau) K_y^a(\tau) \right] d\tau + C_1 \\ &= -\frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \theta'(s) \left[-\sin \theta(s) K_x^a(s) + \cos \theta(s) K_y^a(s) \right] d\tau + C_1 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The corresponding Euler–Lagrange equation yields the general governing equation:

$$EI \frac{d^2\theta}{ds^2} - \frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \left[-\sin\theta(s)K_x^a(s) + \cos\theta(s)K_y^a(s) \right] = 0. \quad (12)$$

3.1. Recovery of Sano's Equation under a Constant Gradient Magnetic Field

We now demonstrate how equation (12) reduces to the classical form for a constant gradient magnetic field $\mathbf{B}^a = by\hat{\mathbf{e}}_y$. For this field, we have:

$$B_x^a = 0, \quad B_y^a = by(s), \quad K_x^a(s) = 0, \quad K_y^a(s) = b \int_s^L y(s') ds'. \quad (13)$$

Substituting into equation (12) gives:

$$EI \frac{d^2\theta}{ds^2} - \frac{AB^r b}{\mu_0} \cos\theta(s) \int_s^L y(s') ds' = 0. \quad (14)$$

Applying Fubini's theorem and relabeling dummy variables as needed, the integral can be simplified, yielding the final planar form:

$$EI \frac{d^2\theta}{ds^2} - \frac{AB^r b}{\mu_0} \left[y(s) \sin\theta(s) - \cos\theta(s) \int_s^L \cos\theta(s') ds' \right] = 0. \quad (15)$$

The expression (15) assumes that the magnetic moment is aligned with the tangent direction of the rod, and it is consistent with the planar governing equation under a constant gradient magnetic field reported by Sano et al. [5], who also adopt the tangent-aligned magnetization assumption. Therefore, this confirms the validity of the equations (12) presented in section (3) for the case of a constant gradient magnetic field with tangent-aligned magnetization. The corresponding simulation results are shown in Fig. 4.

If, instead, the magnetization is assumed along the curve-normal direction, the magnetic moment would be $\mathbf{t}_\perp(s) = (-\sin\theta(s), \cos\theta(s))$. In this case, the magnetic energy integral and the corresponding Euler-Lagrange equation are modified accordingly, yielding a different form of the governing equation:

$$EI \frac{d^2\theta}{ds^2} - \frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \left[-\cos\theta(s)K_x^a(s) - \sin\theta(s)K_y^a(s) \right] = 0 \quad (16)$$

with the corresponding simulation results shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: Comparison of the undeformed configuration with constant magnetic field with field lines perpendicular to the paper plane. In blue is our solution and in red the solution of Sano et al. [5]

Figure 5: Comparison of the undeformed configuration with constant gradient field where the field strength increases linearly with y . In blue is our solution and in red the solution of Sano et al. [5]

3.2. Extension to the $X-Z$ Plane with Gravitational Loading

To extend the preceding $X-Y$ planar formulation to the $X-Z$ plane, we simply replace all occurrences of the transverse coordinate $y(s)$ with $z(s)$. The tangent direction becomes $\mathbf{t}(s) = (\cos \theta(s), \sin \theta(s))$ in the $X-Z$ plane, and the kinematic relations read

$$x'(s) = \cos \theta(s), \quad z'(s) = \sin \theta(s). \quad (17)$$

We now incorporate gravitational potential energy. For a rod of mass density ρ and cross-sectional area A , gravity acts in the negative Z -direction, and the gravitational potential energy is

$$E_{\text{grav}} = \rho A g \int_0^L z(s) ds, \quad (18)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration. The corresponding variational contribution involves nested integrals through

$$z(s) = z(0) + \int_0^s \sin \theta(\sigma) d\sigma. \quad (19)$$

Applying the integral-reduction method introduced in Section 2,

we express the gravitational term in the single-integral form

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{grav}} &= \rho Ag \int_0^L \int_0^s \sin \theta(\sigma) d\sigma ds + C_2 = \rho Ag \int_0^L \int_\sigma^L \sin \theta(\sigma) ds d\sigma + C_2 \\
&= \rho Ag \int_0^L (L - \sigma) \sin \theta(\sigma) d\sigma + C_2 = \rho Ag \int_0^L (L - s) \sin \theta(s) ds + C_2.
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Combining bending, magnetic, and gravitational contributions yields the energy functional

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{tot}} &= \int_0^L \frac{EI}{2} (\theta')^2 ds - \frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \int_0^L \left[B_x^a(s) \cos \theta(s) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + B_z^a(s) \sin \theta(s) \right] ds + \rho Ag \int_0^L (L - s) \sin \theta(s) ds + C_3.
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Introducing the cumulative field functions

$$K_x^a(s) = \int_s^L B_x^a(s') ds', \quad K_z^a(s) = \int_s^L B_z^a(s') ds', \tag{22}$$

and applying the same nested-integral reduction as before (9), the Euler–Lagrange equation becomes

$$EI \theta''(s) - \frac{AB^r}{\mu_0} \left[-\sin \theta(s) K_x^a(s) + \cos \theta(s) K_z^a(s) \right] + \rho Ag(L - s) \cos \theta(s) = 0. \tag{23}$$

This equation constitutes the $X - Z$ -planar analog to the earlier $X - Y$ formulation, now with gravitational loading included. It preserves the compact single-integral structure enabled by the integral-conversion method.

4. Recovery of the Classical 2D Heavy Elastica

We now show that, in the governing equation for planar deformations of hard magnetic rods, setting the magnetic field to zero and accounting for the constraint imposed by the Lagrange multiplier F_1 naturally recovers the

Figure 6: Comparison of the undeformed configuration with constant magnetic field. In addition to figure 4 we have gravitational force in $-z$ -direction (red). The solution of Sano et al. [5] is also represented (blue) to point out the difference to the nongravitational case.

classical heavy elastica model. Consequently, the Euler–Lagrange equation obtained becomes

$$EI \theta''(s) = \lambda g(L - s) \cos \theta(s) - F_1 \sin \theta(s), \quad (24)$$

where $\theta(s)$ is the tangential angle of the centerline.

Equation (24) directly recovers the classical heavy elastica models. Indeed, under the standard choice of the force resultants for a cantilevered or hanging rod, (24) can be rewritten into the form derived by Wang [10]:

$$\theta''(s) = H \sin \theta(s) - (V + Bs) \cos \theta(s), \quad (25)$$

upon identifying

$$H = \frac{-F_1}{EI}, \quad V = \frac{-\lambda g L}{EI}, \quad B = \frac{\lambda g}{EI}. \quad (26)$$

This agreement shows that the classical scenarios analyzed by Wang [10]—including the heavy cantilever, the standing heavy column, and the long hanging column—are all naturally encompassed within our variational formulation. Therefore, the present framework not only accommodates external magnetic loads but also reproduces the full spectrum of two-dimensional heavy elastica configurations, confirming the correctness and robustness of our method.

4.1. The catenary as a degenerate limit of the heavy elastica

Equation (24) contains both bending stiffness and gravitational loading and therefore interpolates between the Euler elastica and the classical catenary.

In the limit $EI \rightarrow 0$, the bending term vanishes and equation (24) reduces to

$$\lambda g(L - s) \cos \theta(s) - F_1 \sin \theta(s) = 0. \quad (27)$$

Using the standard geometric relations for an inextensible curve, this balance yields the classical cosh-catenary profile. A detailed analysis of this limiting transition was given by Wang and Watson [17]. Conversely, when gravitational loading is absent ($\lambda g = 0$), equation (24) reduces to the planar Euler elastica.

Hence, equation (24) consistently connects the Euler elastica and the classical catenary in the two limiting cases. Notably, whereas classical treatments such as Wang and Watson [17] derive the catenary via direct force-balance arguments, the present result follows directly from a single variational principle.

Figure 7: Comparison of the classical catenary and the classical elastica solutions with the heavy elastica solutions. Our solution matches the solution of Wang [10].

5. Discussion

The integral simplification method proposed in this work transforms the originally nested integrals in the energy functional of planar rods into a single integral form through the definition of an accumulation field function. This simplification reduces the complexity of analytical derivations while preserving the physical essence of the system. It also allows for a more direct and intuitive observation of the contributions of different external fields, such as magnetic and gravitational forces, to the rod’s shape. In the application to planar magnetic rods, the method accurately reproduces the deformation patterns reported in previous studies [5], validating its effectiveness under magnetically dominated conditions. Furthermore, the method can be naturally extended to planar rods under gravitational loads, providing a unified framework for both magnetic and gravitational forces without introducing additional mathematical complexity. The planar assumption is generally reasonable in practical engineering scenarios. For instance, in gravity-loaded soft robots, if the magnetic or gravitational force primarily acts along a single direction and the rod has limited bending stiffness, the major bending occurs within a single plane [15]. For weak three-dimensional effects, such as slight out-of-plane torsion or minor lateral deviations, the method can still serve as an approximate tool by superimposing small 3D corrections on the planar solution to estimate rod shape and stress distribution. The robustness of the method is enhanced by the fact that the external field parameters (magnetic field gradient and gravity) are known a priori in this study [16]. The contributions to the energy functional are deterministic, and the governing equations are insensitive to small parameter variations, demonstrating good reliability in engineering simulations. When the magnetic field is zero, the resulting Euler–Lagrange equations reduce to the classical 2D heavy elastica and are fully consistent with Wang’s force-balance approach [10] [17], including typical configurations such as cantilevers, upright heavy rods, and long hanging rods. This indicates that the proposed framework is not only applicable to magnetic loads but also integrates classical heavy-rod analysis, providing a systematic analytical tool for rod-like structures. From a numerical implementation perspective, the single-integral form of the energy functional facilitates the use of standard integration and optimization algorithms, reducing computational effort for predicting planar rod shapes under complex loads. Due to the lack of experimental data and full computational resources, precise quantification and comparison of computational complex-

ity are not feasible; however, theoretically, the single-integral form reduces computational burden and provides potential for future integration with finite element methods to enhance accuracy and applicability.

6. Conclusions

The integral simplification method proposed in this work reduces the energy functional of planar rods under distributed loads to a single integral form while maintaining physical clarity, offering a concise, robust, and systematic analytical tool. The method is applicable to planar rods in gravity-loaded soft robots, magneto-elastic devices, and beams under gravitational loads. It unifies the treatment of magnetic and gravitational forces and can also recover classical planar heavy-rod models, integrating traditional analytical results. Potential applications include precise control of planar flexible magnetic actuators, design of cantilevers and flexible cable structures under gravity, and motion planning and mechanical optimization of soft robots. Future work may include combining this method with finite element approaches to improve accuracy and applicability, developing systematic corrections for weak three-dimensional effects, and conducting sensitivity analysis under complex loads and uncertain external fields, thereby further extending the method's potential for practical engineering applications.

Author contributions

Christopher Tropp: Conceptualization, Resources, Supervision, Writing–review editing;

Yimu Mao: Methodology, Validation, Writing–original draft.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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